

ISic3249

I.Sicily inscription 3249

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Estella Kessler,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 385

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus) s(acrum)

2. Octavius The

3. rmitanus Co

4. mico bene me

5. renti fecit

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Shades of the Underworld. Octavius Thermitanus made it for the well-deserving Comicus.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285128

EDR 121761

EDCS 13300513

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 06.23320 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.1088*259 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 115

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3249. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4357397>